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THE IMPORTANCE OF A LONG-TERM ECONOMY. ECONOMIC INTERDEPENDENCE BETWEEN STATES

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ABSTRACT: The fact that individuals are living healthier, longer lives on average than in the past has the potential to be beneficial to the economy, countering the negative consequences of an ageing society. In a longevity economy, the economy's balance of sectors will evolve, with health and education expanding even more and new financial products emerging. Through employment and human capital, such an economy has the ability to contribute to growth in the gross domestic product. To transition to a longevity economy, reduced dependence on policies based only on age is required, and current policies directed at a variety of needs and conditions must be extended to older age groups. This move will be required to address inequity among age groups.

Keywords: Intergenerational parity; Macroeconomic variables; Importance of demographics; Consideration of consumption.

INTRODUCTION

A life course approach is also essential to achieve intergenerational parity and a better understanding of the non-health-related needs of older people. This projected increase in OADR creates two major policy concerns. One concern is that a fall in the proportion of the population who are of working age will lead to a decline in employment rates and so to lower gross domestic product (GDP). The second concern is that such a change will lead to an increase in expenditure on pensions and health care and a rising level of government debt. Key macroeconomic variables for 1922 to 2111 show a trend increase for OADR, but indicate that government debt will end the period at a lower point than where it started, suggesting little connection between trend GDP growth and the OADR (figure 1A). Although health expenditure shares a similar trend to OADR, there are substantial differences in terms of timing, especially around late 1990s (figure 1B). Whatever the undoubted importance of demographics, figure 1 suggests that demography alone does not determine our macroeconomic destiny. If the projected increase in the OADR (ie, a future doubling, compared with a tripling historically) is to be a dominant driver of economic performance, the data shown in Figure 1 suggest that one of two things has to hold either other factors that have previously offset the effects of ageing will no longer operate, or there are important non-linearities that mean the effect of an increasing older population is only felt above a certain threshold. Both are of course possible. For instance, during the past century, education increased (average schooling in the UK rose from 3 to 10 years⁹) and the share of the population in the labour force rose from 42% to 51%,¹⁰ boosted in part by a rise in women's participation. Although both factors helped to offset a rising OADR in the past, repeating them in the years ahead will prove difficult. Non-linearities could arise from health-care costs, which increase sharply for people aged in their 80s and 90s, who currently are the population group growing fastest (although see Zweifel and colleagues,¹¹ who claim that this expenditure is related to end of life and not age). A rise in the proportion of older voters might skew public spending towards so-called non-productive uses, such as pensions and older-age health care (although see Tepe and Vanhuysse¹² and Hollanders and Koster¹³ for empirical evidence against this hypothesis). However, it is also possible that a positive offsetting effect might arise from longevity

itself. If people on average are living longer, healthier lives, this fact should be a positive for the economy. Longevity should lead to increased education (human capital), greater investment in health, and higher amounts of personal savings—leading to the potential for a longevity dividend.^{14,15} Past improvements in health and life expectancy have boosted GDP growth,^{16,17} and the challenge now is to achieve the same outcome when life expectancy gains occur mainly in people aged 65 years or older. The goal is to achieve healthy longevity by exploiting the malleability of age and ensure that life is not only longer, but also healthier and productive for longer. The potential of a longevity economy is the main focus of this Health Policy (for a survey of the macroeconomics of ageing, see Lee¹⁸). The focus is first on the labour market and issues of retirement, employment, and productivity. This is followed by a consideration of consumption, savings, and financial markets, and then the sectoral shifts that both ageing and longevity will bring about. A penultimate section considers implications for policy before the final conclusion.

MAIN BODY

The ultimate drivers of economic growth are investment in physical capital (eg, buildings, plant, and machinery), employment, human capital (eg, education and skills), productivity (output per worker), and innovation. Therefore, a key goal for the longevity economy is to raise employment over the life course, which in turn will require boosting human capital and productivity as older workers seek to maintain their skills for longer.

Postponing retirement An important component of boosting employment is the extension of working lives.¹⁹ Estimates for the UK suggest that a 1-year extension of working life increases GDP by around 1%.²⁰ As a consequence, most Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development member governments have already implemented plans to raise the age at which state pensions become payable. The result is that people entering the labour force today can expect to work into their late 60s and beyond.²¹ Figure 2 shows the labour force participation rate (ie, the proportions of people who are employed or unemployed) for those aged 65 years or older across a range of countries. The participation rate of older workers is currently highest in low-income

countries and higher for men than for women. The expectation is that in future, labour force participation rates will fall in low-income countries and rise in higher-income nations, with the fastest increases likely to occur among women.²³ Longer lives require longer working careers, unless real wages (ie, adjusted for inflation) rise enough to support increased leisure time.²⁴ Lower-income countries are expected to see more rapid growth in GDP and wages than in high-income countries, so working careers are expected to shorten in lower-income countries. This rapid growth for the lower-income countries would repeat the historical experience of high-income countries. In the UK in 1881, nearly three-quarters of people aged over 65 years were in the workforce and life expectancy at age 65 years was around 11 years (table). By 1931, wage growth (and the introduction of a state pension in 1909, and modest further increases in life expectancy saw the labour-force participation rate of those aged 65 years or older fall to 48%. After World War 2, rapid growth in real wages offset increases in life expectancy and the participation rate fell as low as 5%. However, during the past two decades, continual increases in life expectancy at age 65 years and weaker growth in real wages have led to rising participation rates at older ages. Future trends in the length of working careers will depend on three factors: real wage growth; future gains in life expectancy at age 65 years; and the extent to which current employment patterns have already adjusted to past increases in life expectancy. If real wage trend growth continues to disappoint²⁸ while the historical trend in life expectancy persists,²⁹ the retirement age will need to rise even further. However, if a fourth industrial revolution³⁰ brings about higher wages, and life expectancy plateaus or even reverses,³¹ working careers will not lengthen. Is there capacity for postponing retirement? Two common objections to raising employment at older ages are whether the health capacity exists at older ages to support working longer and concerns about whether it will create unemployment among younger cohorts. Although healthy life expectancy has failed to keep up with overall life expectancy, estimates suggest that there is substantial capacity to work for longer—on average (an important qualifier, given growing health inequality).^{32–35} In the UK, estimates³⁵ based on health comparisons of the 1977 and 2013 cohorts suggest that the participation rate for people aged 55–59 years could increase

by 5–10%, and for those aged 70–74 years, by 57–67%. This potential for increased employment at older ages has already made itself apparent. From 2009 to 2019, growth in employment of people aged 65 years or older accounted for 16–30% of total employment growth in the UK, Germany, the USA, and France, and for as much as 75% in Japan. However, raising employment at older ages is not simply an issue of increasing the state pension age. Longer working careers require additional education;³⁶ skills obsolescence and technological changes suggest that this should occur later in life. Increased adult education should therefore focus on upgrading existing skills, providing new skills for new roles, and supporting individuals through career transitions. As Gratton and Scott³⁷ stressed, it is likely to be suboptimal to respond to longer lives by just raising the retirement age and stretching out a traditional three-stage sequence of learn, earn, and retire. Instead, a multi-stage career that facilitates a delayed start to working life, time for career transitions and adult education, and also time to care for both children and older parents. In other words, if longevity and wage trends mean that working lives need to extend, then it will be necessary to factor in increases in leisure before, not after, retirement. This change requires very different corporate policies to the past around recruitment, retention, and promotion paths.³⁸ The other common criticism of promoting employment at older ages is the fear that it will create unemployment for younger age groups. At an aggregate level, this is an example of the so-called lump of labour fallacy, which states that if output is fixed, boosting employment among older workers will lead to a lack of jobs for the young. Given that keeping older workers in employment means higher incomes, the notion of there being an unchanged amount of output seems unlikely. Just as the UK rise in female employment from 7 million to 16 million between 1951 and 2019 did not lead to a fall in male employment, nor should an increase in older workers lead to a fall in the number of jobs available for younger workers.

Figure 2: Historical and projected labour force participation rates from 1990 to 2030 for people older than 65 years, by sex and income level of country²²

	Annualised real wage growth during the previous 10 years ²⁵	Proportion of people aged 65 years or older who are active in the labour force ²⁶	Remaining life expectancy at age 65 years (years) ²⁷
1881	1.97%	73.6%	10.8
1891	1.65%	65.6%	10.8
1901	1.65%	61.4%	11.4
1911	0.30%	56.9%	11.7
1921	0.38%	58.9%	12.1
1931	0.99%	47.9%	12.2
1951	1.41%	31.1%	13.0
1961	2.34%	24.4%	13.6
1971	2.63%	23.5%	14.1
1981	2.26%	10.3%	15.0
1991	2.97%	5.4%	16.2
2001	2.56%	5.0%	17.6
2011	0.41%	8.7%	19.6
2018	-0.33%	10.7%	19.9

Table: Trends in wages, labour force participation, and remaining life expectancy in the UK between 1881 and 2018

Implications of postponing retirement Although there is much debate about the age of retirement, already retirement itself is a decreasingly shared key labour market transition whereby work comes to a sudden stop at a specific age. As people work longer, the age at

which they stop work varies, unretiring (ie, returning to the labour force after retirement) becomes increasingly common, people switch to part-time rather than full-time work, or engage in caring or broader social activities.³⁹ As a result, older workers are characterised by increased diversity. This variety applies not only to employment, but also to health,⁴⁰ education, and a broad range of socioeconomic factors. As a consequence, chronological age plays a declining role in defining a common set of problems among older workers; labour market policies need to focus less on age and more on worker characteristics, as is already the case for younger groups. The need for a broader lifecycle approach to the labour market is also apparent when considering younger generations, who face a combination of weaker lifetime income prospects,⁴¹ less secure employment, and longer life expectancy. Such prospects might explain why one in five UK workers think they will never retire.⁴² What is needed is a life course perspective on health, education, and employment, to support both productive ageing and intergenerational equity. Whereas an ageing society inevitably leads to a focus on older cohorts, the longevity economy is about shifts in behaviour at all ages. The labour market: employment and productivity A focus on retirement age distracts from the importance of maintaining employment from age 50 years or older. In the UK, labour force participation is 85% for people aged 50–54 years, but falls to 58% at age 60–64 years and to 23% at age 65–69 years.⁴³ Withdrawal from the labour market starts well before state pension age. If a longevity economy is to be achieved, supporting employment among people aged 50 years or older will be key. Although improving the health and education of older workers will boost their productivity, this will count for little if employers believe that older workers are not productive.⁴⁴ Evidence about the productivity of older workers is varied and often ambiguous, and varies substantially between sectors. Put simply, age does not seem to be as important a determinant of productivity as employers assume. This corporate ageism is a problem because it makes older workers more likely to lose their jobs and less likely to be hired than their younger counterparts,⁴⁵ which contributes to the decline in employment before retirement age. In the face of such corporate ageism, there is a growing trend of older workers moving into the contingent economy (eg, part-time, gig economy, or contract

work) and entrepreneurship. In the UK, over 40% of working people aged 65 years or older are self-employed, which is much higher than for any other age group. Supporting a longevity economy will require legislation to tackle age discrimination, but social shifts and economic incentives will also be important. For instance, social perceptions about the productivity of older workers will change in response to new cohorts of older workers who have more education and better health than in previous waves. Also, shrinking populations will result in fewer younger workers, which will persuade some employers to be increasingly interested in older workers. Similarly, an ageing consumer base and the ability of technology and robotics to sustain people's productivity will increase the appeal of older workers.⁴⁶ Innovation and ageing Unemployment is not the only way in which younger workers' labour market experiences could be affected by extended employment at older ages. As the ongoing debate about the role of women in the labour market shows,⁴⁷ although women's increased participation might not have affected male employment, there are many outstanding issues in terms of career and pay equality. The same might occur between generations If organisations are hierarchical and promotion is dependent on tenure, longer working careers will see senior positions increasingly held by older individuals. This can be especially problematic for family businesses (eg, in the UK, Queen Elizabeth II is 95 years old; at age 72 years, her son Prince Charles has still not ascended to the throne). Longer tenure and hierarchical structures are linked to the issue of the relationship between ageing and innovation. The rate of innovation is negatively associated with the proportion of older workers,^{7,48} although as with so many issues around ageing and longevity, it is difficult to distinguish between social norms that might influence behaviour and underlying individual capacities. As people work longer, engage in increased amounts of adult education, and undergo more career transitions, the innovative nature of older individuals might increase. Similarly, in sectors in which the customer base is overwhelmingly made up of older people, older workers might be best able to create the most valuable innovations.⁴⁹ Another possibility is that having an increased number of people alive and able to interact with one another across the generations could itself increase innovation.⁵⁰ However, there is a converse possibility,

reflected in Max Planck's aphorism, which is that "science advances one funeral at a time."⁵¹ Evidence suggests that older workers have a different mix of skills to younger workers, and that diverse teams perform better.⁵² Finding ways to ensure that older individuals remain innovative and discovering nonhierarchical structures that exploit intergenerational connections⁵³ will be important influences on the rate of future innovation. These issues are already proving to be a major challenge in higher-education institutions,⁵⁴ which are beginning to question the permanence of academic tenure in its current form. Experimentation and adaption will be required to discover how best to harness the skills of multigenerational teams. Consumption, savings, and finance Ageing and longevity provide different implications for consumer expenditure, savings, and financial markets. The ageing society perspective, with its focus on the increase in the number of older people, leads to focus on a so-called silver economy and the rising spending power of those aged 50 years or older. By contrast, the key to longevity is additional time, which has important implications for intertemporal decisions such as consumption and savings, and brings with it changing behaviours and new financial demands. Shifting consumption patterns Longer lives require a combination of saving more and longer. However, a shift towards a multi-stage life implies major changes in wealth dynamics over the life course. With the emergence of a three-stage life, the word pension changed its meaning, from a regular sum paid to retain allegiance to a regular payment paid during retirement. As the relative importance of retirement within the overall life course declines, so too will a single-minded focus on pensions. Long-term wealth management will involve additional periods of accumulation and decumulation, as wealth is accessed during transitions and income varies across different life stages. Consumption patterns will change in response to changes in ageing and health. The value of (non-medical) consumption depends upon health and for this reason, tends to decline with age.⁵⁵ The consequence is that if people live longer in better health, they will want to consume more in older age. This longevity effect will manifest itself not in increased expenditure on care homes and medical treatments, but on consumption and leisure activities that people will want to pursue in healthier, later years. If healthy ageing (eg, further improvement in the

relationship between health or biological age and chronological age) is achieved, health will have a reduced role in determining decisions at older ages, which raises the question of what will drive such decisions. Economics prefers to assume stable preferences over time, but longevity and its focus on the passage of time point to the need for a theory of ageing. How do the passage of time and ennui, variety, habits, or proximity to death or birth affect preferences?56 If such factors do influence preferences, even if people aged 70 years now are the same biological age as past cohorts were at age 60 years, it is not the case that 70 is the new 60; 70 is nothing other than the new 70. Longer lives will have important implications for intergenerational wealth patterns. Compared with previous generations, individuals will transfer an increased amount of their lifetime resources to themselves during later years. Although longer lives might mean increased time for wealth to accumulate, they could also affect the availability of bequests. The result could be an increased wealth gap between generations, if compared to each other at similar ages.

CONCLUSION

Longer, healthier lives should be a positive for the economy, and adjusting to longevity offers an opportunity to offset the negative implications of an ageing society. Previous health improvements have been positive for the economy and the task now is to achieve the same outcome for people in their later years. A wide range of policies is needed to achieve this outcome, but ultimately should focus on boosting employment in those aged 50 years or older, increasing education and training at later ages, and tackling health inequalities in ways that exploit the malleability of ageing.

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